

graphia

GRAPHIA

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities

Work Package WP3

Innovative Solutions and Instruments for the SSH KG

Milestone n. 4

Draft Catalogue of innovative workflows for data management and
connection to the SSH KG

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01

Call Topic: R&D for the next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools, methods,
solutions for RI upgrade

Project Start: 2025-01-01

Project Duration: 36 months

Document Identifier: 10.5281/zenodo.17941071

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable Information

WP Number: 3

WP Title: Innovative Solutions and Instruments for the SSH KG

Milestone Number: 4

Milestone Full Title: Definition of total number of innovative workflows

Deliverable Short Title: Workflows draft

Document Identifier: GRAPHIA_WP3_M4_Workflows draft-vn.n

Beneficiary in Charge: CNRS MAP

Report Version: v1.0

Report Submission Date: 2025-12-15

Dissemination Level: PU

Nature: Catalogue

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Keywords: Workflows, Connection, W7

Status: Submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes made
2025/11/25	v0.1	Anthony Pamart	Initial draft
2025/12/12	v0.2	Anthony Pamart	Modified draft
2025/12/14	v1.0	Giovanni Pescarmona	Final draft

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List of Abbreviations

CH	Cultural Heritage
DoA	Description of Action
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HS	Heritage Science
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
KG	Knowledge Graph
LoD	Level of Detail
SSH	Social and Human Sciences
SSHOC	Acronym of the project Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
UC	Use case(s)
WF	Workflow

Executive Summary

This milestone presents the preliminary catalogue of innovative workflows for data management and connection to the SSH KG developed within Task 3.2 of the GRAPHIA project. The catalogue will aggregate and describe ESFRI's workflows, aiming to improve KG-ready or compliant data for WP3 partners serving as Data Providers. This task focuses on the connection of heterogeneous and legacy data to the SSH KG, complementary to T2.4.

The catalogue will establish and document protocols toward the creation of semantic-aware data to create KGs integrable in the GRAPHIA Knowledge Graph (SSH KG). This preliminary version will evolve toward Deliverable D3.2 (M24), which will present the FAIR-by-design workflows to feed GRAPHIA KG with data from the Catalogue of Instruments (T3.1) and Use-Cases (T3.3).

In line with the Description of Action, this milestone clarifies that the catalogue developed in T3.2 includes not only W7-based Cultural Heritage workflows (documentation, provenance, and digital pipelines) but also their explicit relevance for the future connection of heterogeneous and legacy datasets to the SSH Knowledge Graph. While workflows rooted in CH practice remain valid and essential components of the catalogue, they must be articulated with the KG-connection perspective that structures WP3 and the entire GRAPHIA ecosystem. This framing ensures that workflows are not documented solely as operational procedures, but as enablers of semantic-ready, interoperable data flows aligned with the project's long-term objectives.

T3.2 is therefore conceived as a complementary and collaborative effort with the architectural, semantic, and ingestion activities carried out in WP2. T3.2 and WP2 will work together to explore and identify the most effective approaches to achieve the project's KG ingestion objectives. This milestone does not aim to define technical specifications for KG ingestion at this stage; instead, it provides a set of conceptual and methodological foundations that will support a shared and iterative alignment between T3.2 and WP2. As a framing document, it outlines the principles and

structures that will support the production of KG-ready or KG-compliant datasets, acknowledging that detailed mappings, controlled vocabularies, and API-based mechanisms will be formalised in the next phases of WP3. Deliverable D3.2 (M24) will build on this groundwork to provide a consolidated, fully interoperable catalogue aligned with WP2 specifications.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document will initiate the actions to be led within the context of T3.2 Innovative workflows for data management and connection to the SSH KG. The Description of Action will be achieved by the link to this task with other WP3 tasks, namely the T3.1 Catalogue of innovative instruments and T3.3 Use Cases implementation. Cross-WPs collaboration is also required; this document will also present some links between T3.2 and actions from WP2 SSH Knowledge Graph (T2.3 and T2.4) and WP4 Artificial Intelligence Solutions for the SSH KG (T4.1 and T4.3).

This document adopts a high-level approach to introduce how innovative workflows can act as bridges between the operational practices of ESFRI data providers and the semantic requirements of the SSH KG. In particular, it frames W7-based workflow documentation as a **conceptual layer** that captures provenance, methodological context, and digital activity structures. Such a layer is essential to support future mappings to **GoTriple-compliant metadata schemas** and to enable the transformation of CH and HS workflows into **KG-ingestible resources**. By articulating workflows, W7 conceptual models, and the requirements of the SSH KG, this milestone clarifies the position of T3.2 within the GRAPHIA **workflow-to-graph pipeline**.

Recognising that T3.2 is complementary to the work carried out in WP2, this milestone explicitly acknowledges the need to prepare workflows and metadata structures that can evolve toward KG-ready formats. While WP2 defines the semantic architecture, ingestion pipelines, and interoperability standards, T3.2 focuses on **documenting and structuring the processes that produce data**, ensuring that they can be connected to the SSH KG in a transparent, traceable, and FAIR-by-design manner. As such, this milestone positions T3.2 as a foundational activity for the broader GRAPHIA ecosystem and clarifies that more detailed technical specifications will be developed jointly with WP2 during the upcoming phases of WP3.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the **Workflow and Provenance** topics, as necessary contextualization. Section 3 describes the **workflow definition** in a methodological open discussion and potential tools to support the task. Section 4 describes the future actions and strategies to develop the **GRAPHIA catalogue of workflows**.

2. Concepts definitions

The following definitions are provisional and tentative, reflecting open discussions to convey a shared understanding between the partners. The discussion and the update will continue during Task 3.2 until the next deliverable, expected in December 2026.

2.1 Definition of catalogue

Cataloguing is the action of listing and organizing items to ease access to products or services to be used in specific application scenarios. In large-scale research projects, like GRAPHIA, many forms could be adopted for this purpose. A catalogue could be a report of experiments as a deliverable. Past projects in the SSH field have also provided catalogues in the form of web platforms, for example, the Open Marketplace (SSHOC project), which highlights and showcases solutions and research practices for every step of the SSH research data life cycle. Another express catalogue is a Catalogue of Services like the one of E-RIHS, aiming to centralise the management and the access to facilities, techniques and archives distributed throughout Europe. This example would be particularly relevant to avoid the entropy of sparse resources; hence, the integration of innovative workflows within the existing Catalogue of Services would be meaningful, at least to Heritage Science applications. This milestone will temporarily accept those threefold approaches, leaving the decision to adopt one or several forms of cataloguing to coordinated decision-making to be addressed in early 2026.

2.2 Definition of workflow (WF)

A workflow is a series of structured actions or activities to achieve a predefined goal or target. It defines what is done, in what order, by whom or by what, and under which conditions. It serves to organize processes, ensure repeatability, and coordinate actors. Workflows could be guided by rules or logic related to their application domains. Our definition of workflow could encompass two natural extensions of the GRAPHIA framework. On one side, IT manages data and computation internally, while on the other side, ICT ensures that data, systems, and users can connect, communicate, and interact across networks. From an IT point of

view, a workflow is an operative chain linking inputs and outputs. It is a formalized representation of a process executed by systems or software components. While the IT datastream tends to automation or machine orchestration, HMI is also used in workflow management. In the ICT domain, workflows broaden automated sequences to integrated pipelines interacting with tools, data and users. For this reason, a GRAPHIA-oriented definition of workflow would be both technical and methodological. In this context, **workflow management** is mandatory for open science principles, leveraging interoperability to foster transparency and reproducibility. In this perspective, some intrinsic concepts of workflow toward an open framework for KG are data provenance, traceability, and lineage. Insofar, creating a catalogue of workflows implies a reinforced provenance tracking of current practices, more especially in SSH, where activities to construct data streams are heterogeneous from one sub-domain to another (e.g. Heritage Science, Geospatial, Religious or Gender studies, to name a few represented in the GRAPHIA project).

2.3 Tentative definition of the Catalogue of innovative workflows

The common space to define and trace “workflow” in GRAPHIA is the digital realm. By considering both digital-born and digitalized resources¹, there is a space to define workflow as a series of digital or digitalization activities. Different Levels of Detail (LoDs) still have to be considered to fit ESFRI’s needs as Data Providers. At the atomic level, workflow could be a Digital Activity linking an input to an output, just the action of linking two data (e.g. Data to Metadata). A minimal approach is the operative chain taking as a source an input to deliver an output using specified Digital Activities. Ideally, a workflow would be a triplet composed of source data and a derivation linked by stabilized and documented Digital Activities. Downstream, one considers data collection or capture as closest to raw data. Upstream, one considers a semantically enriched and KG-ready instance of the source data. In between, a digital activity related to the processing step. A workflow is supposed to be linear, with a beginning and an end, but the linkage from the input to the output could be, in practice, way more complex. One could think of an input sequentially derived with

¹Smith, A., & Whearty, B. (2023). All the work you do not see: Labor, digitizers and the foundations of digital humanities. *Debates in the digital humanities*, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis.

several processing steps before a final version of the output (i.e pre-processing, processing, post-processing) to compose a schematic WF. Also, the linear vision is restrictive, as one refers today to the data life cycle, workflow could also be a closed loop. Linear vision is also prohibitive to represent iterative and or recursive activities or chains of activities composing realistic WF leading to ESFRI's practitioners' workflows.

Fig 1. Examples of realistic workflow nodes organising and structuring time-oriented relations between digital activities: a) chain, b) parallel sequences, c) knot, d) iterative sequences, e) repetitive sequences (credits: Dudek, 2023)².

Ultimately, to be able to manage data and workflow for KG connection, a workflow should be expressed as Triplets:

Input data *is transformed* by Digital Activity *generating* an Output.

Several ontologies could be used to stabilize the workflow description, like wfdesc³, wfprov⁴, Open Provenance Model for Workflows (OPMW)⁵, or OntoMetaWorkflow⁶, but the most logical would be the extension of PROV (ProvONE) already considered in GRAPHIA and compliant with the framework proposed in the following sections.

² Source and credits (Dudek, 2023): Iwona Dudek, Jean-Yves Blaise. Research workflows, paradata, and information visualisation: feedback on an exploratory integration of issues and practices - MEMORIA IS. Peer Community In Archaeology, 2023, <10.5281/zenodo.8311129>. <halshs-04091200v2> - page 8.

³ <https://vocab.linkeddata.es/ontologies/purl.orgwf4everwfdesc.html>

⁴ <https://vocab.linkeddata.es/ontologies/purl.orgwf4everwfprov.html>

⁵ <https://www.opmw.org/index.html>

⁶ https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-25274-7_21

These technical choices will be discussed among the partners in the next step of WP3 and other GRAPHIA WPs.

WP2 sets the GoTriple model as a requirement for the KG connection. The management of workflows requires associating the resource-based approach (output) with an event (or activity) oriented model.

Preliminary definitions:

Input = Define the data source and describe the data collection modality. An input could be a single resource or a collection of resources.

Digital activity = Define any kind of digital operation (capturing, processing, filtering, refinement, optimization, enhancement, curation or enrichment) affecting data and/or metadata generating new input or output data (i/o).

Output = Define a new formalization of data that will populate GRAPHIA KG. An output is a single or multiple data expressed in a compliant format to feed the KG. Outputs are the resources considered as entry points for SSH KG.

Tentative workflows at different LoD:

LOD 1 - Atomic WF = Input = Digital Activity = Output

Example of atomic WF : (Input) Data *is described* by metadata (Output)

LOD 2 - Minimal WF = Data collection (Input) > Data processing (Digital Activity) > Data Enrichment (Output)

Example of minimal WF = (Input) A raw metadata description *is structured* in a metadata scheme (Output)

LOD 3 - Ideal WF = Image Data acquisition (Input) > Photogrammetric Data processing (Digital Activity) > 3D model (Output)

Example of minimal WF = (Input) An image set *is processed* by Structure from Motion algorithm *to generate* a colored sparse pointcloud (Output)

LOD 4 - Schematic WF: Data collection (Input) > Pre-processing (Filtered data) > Processing (Optimized data) > Post-processing (Enriched data) > Data Analysis (Output)

Example of Schematic WF = (Input) A raw image set is *calibrated* by image processing algorithm to *export* TIFF format (i/o) *computed* in Meshroom to *generate* dense point cloud (i/o) and camera poses (i/o) *enriched* by semantic annotation (i/o) to *create* segmented point clouds (Outputs).

3. Workflows definitions

3.1 Defining the approach to construct the catalogue of workflows

Nowadays, data providers like the ESFRI's partners generate **heterogeneous data** with a remaining gap with FAIR by design principles and unstandardized workflows. KG-ready data is reachable for workflows anticipating semantic enrichment, while KG compliance has to be improved for legacy data. WP3 will produce data through instruments and use-cases. Task 3.2 will tackle data compliance and readiness with innovative workflows to **facilitate semantic descriptions for KG connection**. In order to fill the knowledge gap, a hypothesis is made that a **data-provider friendly conceptual model** is a key tool to improve data compliance and readiness for SSH KG connection. The proposal made in this document is to set W7 as a transversal semantic framework to build the catalogue of workflows.

The **W7 model** (Who, What, When, Where, Why, Which, How) is introduced in this milestone as an intermediate conceptual layer that bridges practical workflows and formal semantic representations. While workflows capture the operational sequence of activities performed during data acquisition, processing, and enrichment, they rarely provide explicit, structured descriptions of the actors, motivations, tools, outputs, and contextual conditions involved. The W7 model fills this gap by offering a universal and lightweight schema capable of documenting each activity in a workflow through seven core dimensions. This makes implicit knowledge explicit, and transforms heterogeneous, tacit or undocumented practices into structured, analysable information.

3.2 The W7 framework

The W7 is a conceptual model dedicated to **data provenance** initiated by Ram and Liu in 2009. The name of W7 is inspired by the 6W+1H method, referring to a simplistic yet efficient answer to inquire about a resource or a process, namely: What? Who? Where? When? Which? Why? and How? The W7 model proposed to link upper-class concepts like Object, Agent, Space, Time, Instrument, Cause and Reason to provide sense-making relationships between those concepts. The strength — at

Fig 2. Screenshot of Quasimodo platform showing a graph-based W7 provenance exploration of Notre-Dame de Paris KG-ready HDT (credits: De Luca, 2025)⁹

This W7-based structuring constitutes a crucial preparatory step before ingestion into a SSH Knowledge Graph. It provides a harmonised semantic surface from which richer ontological models (e.g. PROV-O, CIDOC-CRM, or project-specific vocabularies) can be derived in a systematic way. In practical terms, the W7 description functions as a pivot: it captures the essential meaning behind activities and data transformations, enabling consistent mapping to KG entities and relations, regardless of disciplinary vocabularies or local documentation standards. Thus, W7 enhances interoperability, improves the quality of the metadata entering the KG, and ensures that workflow-derived resources can be aligned, queried, and reused within the broader SSH semantic ecosystem.

W7 and GoTriple are not competing models but complementary layers that capture different facets of the research process. W7 focuses on activities — how data are produced, by whom, with which tools, where and why — while GoTriple focuses on the resulting research resources and how they can be shared, discovered and reused in the SSH ecosystem. Because activities produce resources, a natural continuity exists between the approaches: W7 documents the context, provenance and meaning behind research actions, and GoTriple provides the semantic structure for exposing the resulting datasets, methods, software or publications. Using W7 as an **intermediate layer** therefore enriches GoTriple-compatible resources with clearer provenance and contextual grounding, while allowing workflows and practices to remain fully traceable.

3.3 The ANAMNESIS web-application for W7 metadata and paradata management of CH and HS documentation

ANAMNESIS is an open-source platform for collaboratively creating and managing dynamic metadata and paradata for CH and HS instrumentation-based documentation workflow. It is included in GRAPHIA's Catalogue of innovative instruments as a software compound of the HYPERMNESIA framework dedicated to workflow provenance for HS applications. It has been developed by an eponym

⁹ Source and credits (De Luca, 2025) : ERC Advanced Grant NDame Heritage

project funded by the French Foundation of Heritage Science (FSP) in 2024 to contribute to the French HS infrastructure project EQUIPEX+ ESPADON. The FSP is holding the national node of E-RIHS France, insofar as GRAPHIA is a logical extension to test and update the tool ANAMNESIS to a European scale. This prototype is currently hosted and maintained in the ESPADON distributed computing infrastructure, but is ready for new instance deployment (Docker-based). This innovative tool is currently being integrated into the E-RIHS Catalogue of Service as DIGILAB. ANAMNESIS, in its current stage of development, enables a user-based documentation of digital activities through the W7 structure. The W7 implementation introduces a small adaptation to the W7 scheme and states the following classes to define a **Digital Activity**:

- WHAT: Digital Entity (i.e. a data resource in its digital or digitalized form) and a Material Entity (i.e. the physical object itself)
- WHERE: Location
- WHO: Agents (individual and or institution)
- WHEN: Temporal information
- HOW: Methods and techniques
- WHICH: Instruments (i.e tools, software, devices, etc.)
- WHY: Context (i.e projects, etc.)

The activities belong to different stages of CH documentation from digitization practices with dedicated schemas. Schemas can be created, modified and shared by expert users with Admin roles directly within the interface. ANAMNESIS enables the stabilization of 5W with perennial semantic identifiers:

- WHAT: DOI, Ark, Uri
- WHERE: GeoNames, or WhatThreeWord
- WHO: HAL API (to be linked to ORCID)
- WHEN: ISO Standard or PeriodO
- WHY: HAL API (linked to CORDIS)

The last 2Ws (HOW and WHICH) interlink instruments and their specific modalities used in the activity are stabilized by user-defined concepts (OpenTheso) or by other perennial identifiers (URI, ARK, Handle).

ANAMNESIS enables the creation of W7 structured metadata schemas to document digital activities that are exported in JSON format. The Import features enable the platform to be fed with new schemes and a conflict management system, which

keeps the database clean. The platform also enables users to create templates to support batch processing. The export feature includes a mapping functionality to transform the output to other metadata schemas (GoTriple, Dublin Core, EDM). Metadata descriptions could be gathered in user-customised Collections and could be shared using different visibility parameters (public, private, confidential) to be enriched dynamically and collaboratively. ANAMNESIS is already available in open-source (licence GNU AGPLV3)¹⁰ and a testing instance is available¹¹.

Fig 3. Current overview of the ANAMNESIS platform (Credit: Pamart, 2025).

¹⁰ https://gitlab.espadon.net/anamnesis/anamnesis_monorepo

¹¹ <https://anamnesis.espadon.net/>

3.4 Tentative methodology for workflows description to be managed in the Catalogue

In this section, all partners involved in the task are invited to describe their most common workflow in natural language (or a matrix form to be discussed in 2026). The main idea is to evaluate the compliance or readiness level of workflows to be managed to tailor the best methodological and technological approach. The task leader and the partners will conduct a self-evaluation of the FAIRness of their workflow to be described by semantic layers (GoTriple, W7, EDM, PROV, and others).

List of 3.2 participants (PM involvements) and expected inputs:

CNRS MAP (18PM) - Workflows catalogue, WF description (expected numbers of WF = 3)

CNR (9PM) - Workflows description (expected numbers of WF 1)

UNIBO (9PM) - Workflows description (expected numbers of WF = 1)

CYI (5PM) - Workflows description (expected numbers of WF = 1)

Foxcub (5PM) - Interoperability assessment and development

TIB (5PM) - Interoperability assessment and development

Net7 (3PM) - Interoperability assessment and development

KNAW (2PM) - Interoperability assessment and development

3.4.1 Draft template for workflow description

Based on the tools of the catalogue of instruments (T3.1) in relation to the use cases (T3.3), try to summarize the most generic and conventional workflow, including data collection/acquisition, data processing and data analysis activities.

Workflow textual description: The workflow of [Name of the Partners] starts with a data collection performing [Type of the Tools and Instruments] using [Type of Technique] generating [Type of input and Data source]. The input data sources are transformed by [single or multiple] processing step generating [Type of output and Data output] using [Type of the Tools and Instruments]. This output is [intermediary or final]. If intermediary, this intermediary data are transformed by [single or multiple] a new [Processing or Analysis] step consisting of [Data filtering, optimization, extraction, annotation, segmentation, enrichment, enhancement, fusion] generating [Type of output and Data output] using [Type of the Tools and Instruments]. Repeat this sentence until Final output to be integrated in GRAPHIA KG is obtained.

Type of application domain: CH documentation, Heritage Science, Geospatial, Digital Humanities and studies

Type of workflows: Linear, cyclic or both

Type of technique: Either generic (Real-based modeling / Image Capture), intermediary (Image-based modeling / 2D scanning) or specific (Photogrammetry / Photography)

Type of the Tools and Instruments: Name of the instruments or tools (acquisition device, software, etc.)

Type of input: Single, multiple or variable

Type of Intermediary Data: Single, multiple or variable

Type of output: Single, multiple or variable

Type of Data source: Most used file type (text, image, audio, table, 3D model) and format

Type of Data output: Most used file format (text, image, audio, table, 3D model)

Metadata and paradata of input, intermediary and output: Yes or no, technical and/or descriptive.

Metadata scheme or standard used: Example (EXIF, DublinCore, Europeana Data Model, etc.)

Workflow formalization: Type of data collection, type of data processing, type of data analysis

3.4.2 Generic workflow description of [MAP-CNRS]

Based on the tools of the catalogue of instruments (T3.1) in relation to the use cases (T3.3), MAP-CNRS summarizes its most conventional workflow, including data collection/acquisition, data processing and data analysis.

Workflow textual description: The workflow of MAP-CNRS starts with a data collection performed by Real-based capture using Photogrammetry and generating multiple image sets as input. The input data sources are transformed by a single processing step, generating a pointcloud and spatialized images using commercial or FLOSS image-based modeling software. This output is intermediary. This intermediary data is transformed by multiple outputs by a new digital activity step consisting of annotation and segmentation, generating a semantically enriched 3D model composed of several file types using the web platform AIOLI. Occasionally, this process is iterated on different parts of CH objects at different temporalities to construct HDT, aiming to be integrated in GRAPHIA KG.

Type of application domain: CH documentation and Heritage Science

Type of workflows: Linear

Type of technique: Generic (Real-based modeling), intermediary (Image-based modeling) or specific (Photogrammetry)

Type of the Tools and Instruments: SPIDER, STUDIO or ARCH photogrammetry rig combined with 3D modeling software (Metashape, MicMac, Meshroom) integrated in the AIOLI spatial annotation platform

Type of input: Multiple

Type of output: Multiple

Type of Data source: Image set (RAW+JPG)

Type of Intermediary Data: 3D Pointcloud (PLY)

Type of Data output: Segmented 3D models (PLY), vectors (SVG), images (JPG), table (CSV), and text (JSON).

Metadata and paradata of input, intermediary and output: Yes, technical and descriptive.

Metadata scheme or standard used: EXIF and W7

Workflow formalization: Real-based modelling for data collection, photogrammetric processing, and semantic enrichment through annotation for data analysis.

In this example, formalized from UC 003 (Data ingestion & enrichment for architectural digital twins), we will mobilize innovative instruments mentioned in UC-040 to UC-043 of the GRAPHIA SSH KG - Use cases Matrix (internal file). The workflow is constructed and semantically enriched from the data source to its KG connection. This data corpus is typical of KG-ready ESFRI's source, requiring a metadata mapping to fit the minimal requirement of the GoTriple model to be integrable into SSH KG.

4. Conclusion

As mentioned in the DoA, a W7 structured approach of CH workflows (documentation, provenance, pipelines) is a valid component of the catalogue in order to support KG connection perspectives. Starting in January 2026, T3.2 will focus on WP3 serving as the Data Provider to feed GRAPHIA KG by standardizing interoperable connections with T2.4. These further technical specifications regarding intraoperative processes will be developed during the next phases of WP3.

4.1 Roadmap for the implementation of the Catalogue of workflow

Proposal of actions, subtask's deadlines to formalize the catalogue of workflows expected to be delivered in December 2026.

- Early 2026, necessity of validation from WP leaders (mostly W7 compliance) internal meeting scheduled
- Early 2026, translation of the Front-End in English
- First semester 2026, WF description to HS instruments (T3.1) and UCs (T3.3)
- First quarter 2026, mapping of W7 metadata to GoTriple
- Second quarter 2026, ad-hoc WF activities schemes for GRAPHIA WF (LLM4SSH, etc)
- Third quarter 2026, extension to SSH workflows
- October 2026, draft catalogue based on the existing user-friendly prototype tool ANAMNESIS (TRL similar to Quagga)
- Last quarter 2026, delivery of the Catalogue of Workflows and interconnection with GRAPHIA (API)

In addition, a necessary task meeting has to be planned (summer or third quarter 2026) in physical or hybrid format in Marseille (MAP-CNRS) or Florence (Headquarters of E-RIHS) with the form of a datathon aiming for the co-construction of workflow and interoperability solving.

Fig 4. Graphical overview of workflow management within ANAMNESIS, current state (up), ongoing (middle) and expected (bottom) (Credit: Pamart 2025).